

COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION IN A NEWLY DEVELOPED ENCAPSULATED AND BRAIDED ANNEALED GRAPHITE EPOXY COMPOSITE RADIATOR IN A SPACECRAFT.

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ABSTRACT

A vital part of space vehicle design is the thermal control subsystem. An important issue in the design of the thermal control subsystem is the localized concentration of heat dissipation; high dissipating electronic devices have a very high heat density over a small footprint area to the radiator panel. The design of large spacecraft structures constructed with more than one material must give careful attention to the mechanical loads introduced by the thermal growth resulting from dissimilar coefficient of thermal expansion CTEs; hence there is a great need for structural compatibility between the doublers and the spacecraft bus radiator which is not the case with embedded aluminum heat pipe. Higher thermally conductive polymer composites are currently been used as sink to dissipate the heat produced by such electronic components. Therefore alternative advanced thermal materials are needed to meet future spacecraft thermal radiator requirements to ensure compatibility with doublers or can even be used without doublers. This paper seeks to computationally model the Temperature distribution in a newly developed encapsulated and braided annealed graphite epoxy composite radiator to determine its thermal and structural performance. A simulation programme will be initiated to verify the ability of this new material concept to meet performance requirements in an operational environment which includes significant thermal cycles representative of launch loads.

NOMENCLATURE

C Proportionality constant.
conductivity function.

$F(x)$ Integral of one over the spatially-
dependent thermal conductivity function.

K Thermal conductivity.

L Length.

Q Heat rate.

T Temperature.

X One-dimensional x-coordinate.

A Area of cross section, m^2

C Specific heat, J/kgK

H_{lv} Latent heat of vaporization, J/kg

h_o Heat transfer coefficient, $W/m^2 K$

k Thermal conductivity, W/mK

L Length of the heat pipe, m

P Perimeter, m

Q Heat, W
 Q/A Heat flow rate, W/m²
 R Universal gas constant, J/kgK
 Re Reynolds number
 R_{min} Minimum meniscus radius, m
 R_w Radius of the wire, m
 r Radius of the meniscus, m
 t Time, s
 u Axial velocity, m/s
 v Velocity, m/s
 Y One-dimensional y-coordinate.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the composite materials have a wide range of applications depending on the temperature therefore it is necessary to study the thermal characteristic of the materials. Very often composite materials results in anisotropic media and their thermal conductivity changes along the axis because of the presence of reinforcing fibers embedded in the matrix [Oronzio Manca, Biagio Morrone]. The thermal response of an anisotropic medium subject to thermal disturbance can be determined by means, of numerical procedures or experimental setups [Oronzio Manca, Biagio Morrone]. The ability of the composite material to resist or conduct heating depends on the quantities and qualities of the constituents. Most of the work is concentrated on determining the temperature and heat flux distribution of the composite specimens at different loads. Pilling et.al studied the effect of fiber volume fraction and the fiber orientation on the thermal conductivity of carbon fiber-reinforced composites. Gaglord mentioned that the composite materials have anisotropic properties; therefore it has high thermal conductivity along the fiber direction and low thermal conductivity in a direction perpendicular to the fiber direction. Manca et.al studied the thermal response of the composite materials by evaluating the thermal response of the specimens to

different heating conditions. James and P. Harrison used the finite difference method in the calculation of temperature distribution and heat flow in composite materials made from anisotropic materials. Zhan-Shang Guo et.al studied the experimental and numerical temperature distribution of thick polymeric matrix laminates. The finite element formulation of transient heat transfer problem was carried out for polymeric matrix composite materials from the heat transfer differential equations. BSR Murthy et.al studied the analysis of thermal stresses, temperature distribution across the composite thick plates by using physical model and two dimensional finite element models for three different filter materials with epoxy as matrix material. Rondeaux et al developed a specific thermal conductivity measurement facility for preimpregnated fibers glass epoxy composite, where the thermal conductivity measurements are presented in the temperature of 4.2 K to 14 K for different thicknesses. A vital part of the space vehicle design, the thermal control subsystem must maintain all components at or below specified allowable operational temperature limits when exposed to external thermal environments. Alternative advanced thermal materials are needed to meet future spacecraft thermal radiator subsystem requirements. To satisfy that need, Northrop Grumman Space Technology implemented a breakthrough concept of encapsulated annealed pyrolytic graphite (APG) for thermally stressing spacecraft applications and further modifications were carried out to obtain Braided Annealed graphite Epoxy Composite Radiator.

PHYSICAL MODELING

We describe a method for modeling the thermal conductivity and temperature profile in a newly developed encapsulated and braided annealed graphite epoxy composite radiator. The radiator consists of a random

binary composite, whose concentration varies in the direction perpendicular to the radiator surface, and a fixed temperature difference is applied across one end of the radiator. In the first method, the temperature profile is modeled directly, using a finite element technique in which the film is represented as a discrete network of thermal conductance, randomly distributed according to the assumed composition profile. The temperature at each node, and the effective thermal conductance, is then obtained by a transfer matrix technique.

Our model for the Braided Annealed graphite Epoxy composite radiator is quite simple. Our goal here is to compute transient temperatures profiles for 1-D that can be converted into 2D or 3D heat conduction in the material during the heating process. The boundary condition chosen in both bottom and top surfaces of the model are kept constant and equal to 125°C and 20°C describing acceptance limits in panels and doublers in a spacecraft. Subsequent heat loads were chosen depicting thermal cycle test of a spacecraft. The sides of the model are assumed to be insulated. The initial temperature is 20 C. The specific gravity is 2.4gm/cm³. The in plane thermal conductivity is 1300 W/mK. The electrical resistivity is 240μΩ/cm.

SPACECRAFT THERMAL CONTROL SUBSYSTEM AND FUTURE MISSION NEEDS

A spacecraft thermal control subsystem must simultaneously accomplish the following: Maintain all components at or below specified allowable operational temperature limits. Dissipate heat at a radiator temperature of 40°C or higher to maximize thermal efficiency, i.e., minimize the thermal gradient between the chip and the radiator. Minimize the mass of components in the heat rejection path.

Table 1 lists typical spacecraft temperature requirements. A relatively cool, narrow operating temperature range extends the useful life of batteries. Propulsion systems, on the other hand, may need a warm environment to avoid freezing propellants, i.e., hydrazine. To meet long-duration space mission reliability requirements, junction temperature limits for the electronic components on the printed circuit boards are typically 105°C for silicon components and 125°C for GaAs components. The heat generated by spacecraft components often presents difficult thermal design problems because of local high heat fluxes (typically expressed as W/in²), high total power dissipation, and wide temperature changes over time (e.g., a satellite moving in and out of the sun's rays is subjected to large cyclic temperature extremes over short periods of time). Heat sources include communication system transmitters and receivers; spacecraft electronics, such as attitude control, electrical power, and telemetry and command; batteries; solar cells; and semiconductor chips. The increasing need to fly larger, higher-performance payloads with higher-density microprocessors for longer periods of time has escalated power dissipation and heat flux at the silicon level. Future military communication satellites will have higher power density microelectronics packaging design concepts that will increase by five to ten times the data processing throughput, resulting in up to ten times the thermal density requirements, e.g., power dissipation will increase from 2 to 3 W/in² above the current level of 0.1 to 0.5 W/in².

Consequently, the chip junction-to-unit base-plate temperature gradients can exceed 80°C. If waste heat is not efficiently removed from the electronic devices and components.

Table 1 Typical spacecraft temperature requirements

Component	Temperature Range (°C)
Chips	<125
Electronic equipment	0 to 50
Batteries	5 to 20
Propulsion tanks and lines (hydrazine)	5 to 50
Solar arrays	-100 to +75

Table from Northrop Grumman Space Technology Review journal.

Electronics packaging designers must therefore increase component density and reject additional thermal dissipation, while improving component reliability and performance for such advanced chips as GaAs. Passive thermal components such as radiators, doublers, multilayer insulation, coatings, chassis enclosures, and chip packaging are often used to control the temperatures of electronic components. Required in all spacecraft, radiators are designed in several forms, such as structural equipment panels, flat-plate radiators mounted to the side of the spacecraft, and panels deployed after the spacecraft is on orbit. Driven by future stringent weight and thermal performance requirements, the next generation of satellites will potentially use higher thermally conductive materials in the design of the electronics boxes, chip packaging, radiators, and heat-spreading doublers.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The models you specify determine the Governing Equations that will be used. Starting from the energy transport equation:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}}_{\text{transient}} + u \underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial x}}_{\text{convection}} = \underbrace{\frac{k \partial^2 T}{\rho c_p \partial x^2}}_{\text{diffusion}} - \underbrace{\frac{Q}{\rho c_p}}_{\text{source}} \quad (1)$$

For our problem, the temperatures are dependent on times; there is no fluid flow and no source terms. The only mode of heat transfer is by diffusion. So the problem is a transient diffusion problem with no convection but heat source. So the governing equation changes to;

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}}_{\text{transient}} = \underbrace{\frac{k \partial^2 T}{\rho c_p \partial x^2}}_{\text{diffusion}} + \underbrace{\frac{k \partial^2 T}{\rho c_p \partial y^2}}_{\text{diffusion}} - \underbrace{\frac{Q}{\rho c_p}}_{\text{source}} \quad (2)$$

This is a two dimensional poisson equation.

The equation can be formulated in finite element form with shape function below.

$$\frac{\delta \Pi}{\delta d_j} = \int_{\Omega} \left[k_x \left(\sum \frac{\partial N^i}{\partial x} d_i \right) \frac{\partial N^j}{\partial x} + k_y \left(\sum \frac{\partial N^i}{\partial y} d_i \right) \frac{\partial N^j}{\partial y} \right] d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} Q N^j d\Omega - \int_{\partial \Omega} \bar{q} N^j d\Gamma \quad (3)$$

With characteristics,

$$[K_{ji}] \{d_i\} = \{f_j\} \quad (4)$$

$$k_{ab}^e = k_{ab}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \left[k_x \frac{\partial N^a}{\partial x} \frac{\partial N^b}{\partial x} + k_y \frac{\partial N^a}{\partial y} \frac{\partial N^b}{\partial y} \right] d\Omega \quad (5)$$

$$= k_x \begin{bmatrix} k_{11} & k_{12} & k_{13} \\ k_{21} & k_{22} & k_{23} \\ k_{31} & k_{32} & k_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\equiv \int_{\Omega^e} [B^a]^T [D] [B^b] d\Omega$$

$$f_a = \int_{\Omega^e} Q N^a d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^e} \bar{q} N^a d\Gamma$$

$$k_{ab}^e = k_{ba}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} [B^a]^T [D] [B^b] d\Omega = \int [B^a]^T [D] [B^b] j d$$

$$k_{ab}^e = k_{ba}^e \approx \sum_{j=1}^{Nrt} ([B^a]^T [D] [B^b] j)_{(\xi_j, \eta_j)} w_j$$

$$f_a = \int_{\Omega^e} Q N^a d\Omega = \int Q N^a j d \approx \sum_{j=1}^{Nrt} (Q N^a j)_{(\xi_j, \eta_j)} w_j \quad (7)$$

Algorithms and codes were developed as subroutines to obtain the temperature distribution and Heat flux along the composite material.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The composite specimens were made from annealed graphite epoxy composite with different fiber volume fraction and different fiber orientation and the study was made using finite element technique. For composites of this nature *Rolfes (200)* has proposed a linear thermal lamination theory which is analogous to the first order shear deformation theory (FSDT). For local effects or transient problems the same author has suggested a quadratic thermal lamination theory. Subsequently, new 2D element formulations are outlined which are based on layerwise linear or quadratic temperature distributions. The different Figures show the temperature distribution contours of the composite specimens under different case study of heat source reminiscence of thermal loading during thermal cycle test.

Fig 1. Transient Temperature distribution on the composite structure.

Fig 2. Conductive Heat Flux along the Composite structure.

Fig 3. Transient Total Heat flux along the composite structure.

Fig 4 Temperature Gradient along the composite structure.

Fig 7. Extrusion plot of temperature distribution along the composite structure.

Fig 5 Total Heat Flux along x- component.

Fig 8. Total heat flux on the Composite structure

Fig 6. Total Heat Flux along y-component.

Fig 9. Conductive Heat Flux on the composite structure.

Fig 10. Contour plots of temperature distribution along the length of Composite structure.

Fig 11. Contour plots of Total heat flux along the length of the Composite structure.

CONCLUSIONS

The newly developed encapsulated and braided annealed graphite epoxy composite material was analyzed extensively in various thermal cycling modes and using finite element method. The temperature distribution and heat flux pattern clearly shows that this newly developed material can act as a good transporter, distributor and conserver of large amount of heat. This makes it suitable to be used as a doubler, encapsulation for heat pipes and radiator for high heat dissipating equipments e.g. TWTA'S in satellites and other spacecrafts.

REFERENCES

- 1 Oronzio Manca, Biagio Morrone, Giuseppe Romano, “**Analysis of Thermal Response of Composite Materials**”, Dipartimento Ingegneria Aerospaziale e Meccanica, <http://event.ua.pt/ds2005/manca3.pdf>. Italy, (2005).
2. Pilling M.W., Yates B., Black,M.A. “**The Thermal Conductivity of Carbon Fiber – Reinforced Composites**”, Journal of Materials Science, Vol.14, (1979).
3. Gaglord M.W., “**Reinforced Plastic Theory and Practice**”, 2nd edition, Chahnenrs Put. Co. Inc., (1974).
4. James K.U., Sura, S. “Study of Thermal Characteristics of a composite specimen Experimentally and by Using Finite element Method”, Eng & Tech Vol. 26, (2008).
5. Hui P.M., Zhang X., Markworth A.J.,Stroud D., “**Thermal conductivity of graded composites: Numerical simulations and an effective medium approximation**” Journal of materials science 34 (1999) 5497 – 5503.
6. Edward M. S., “**Product Development of Engineered Thermal Composites for Cooling Spacecraft Electronics**” Technology Review Journal Fall/Winter 2005.
7. Oller S., Martínez X., Barbat A., Rastellini F.; “**Advanced Composite Material Simulation**” Ciencicie Tecnologia dos Materials Vol 20. 2008.
8. Tessmer J., Rolfes R., 2D “**Thermal Analysis of Hybrid Structure**” DLR Institute of Structural Mechanics 1991
9. Rahbar N., “**Introduction to Finite Element Method**” AUST class presentation 2011.